

RESPONSE OF BIOSTIMULANTS ON YIELD AND QUALITY OF WHEAT

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Abstract

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a crucial staple crop globally, particularly in India, where it contributes significantly to food and nutritional security. Biostimulants enhanced with fulvic and humic acids offer a promising solution by improving soil fertility, plant growth, and resistance to abiotic stresses. The present study was conducted at the Experimental Farm of the Inter-Faculty Department of Irrigation Water Management, MPKV, Rahuri during the Rabi season of 2023-2024 and evaluated the impact of biostimulants on wheat growth and yield, applying them via seed dressing, soil application and foliar sprays. A randomized block design was employed, featuring 14 treatments with three replications across 42 plots, each measuring 1.5 m × 7.5 m. Wheat (variety Phule Samadhan) was sown mechanically at a 0.20 m row spacing. The results showed that biostimulants, particularly when combined with 100% recommended dose (RD) of NPK and foliar sprays, significantly improved wheat growth parameters, including plant height, tiller count, panicle length, and grain yield. The treatment combining 100% RD of NPK with two foliar sprays of biostimulant powder at 3 g L⁻¹ (T₁₀) yielded the highest results in plant population, panicle length, grain count and 1000-seed weight, followed by treatments T₉ and T₁₃. T₁₀ also achieved the maximum grain yield (49.29 q ha⁻¹) and straw yield (68.22 q ha⁻¹), while the control (T₁) had the lowest. Improvements in protein content, gluten content, and hectolitre weight were most notable in T₁₀, likely due to enhanced nutrient uptake and efficient utilization. These findings highlight the potential of biostimulants to boost wheat productivity and nutritional quality while reducing dependence on synthetic fertilizers.

Keywords: Wheat, Biostimulants, Yield, Quality

Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a staple food for millions of people worldwide and is known as the "king of cereals" and the "stuff of life.". It is essential to global agriculture and food security. Wheat is the second most important cereal crop in India and plays a major role in the food and nutritional security of the country, particularly in North India. Over half of the world's population gets 20% of their calories from wheat, and because of the special qualities of gluten, baked goods are the main food consumed in Western nations (Shewry, P. R., 2002). Nutritionally, wheat is a well-rounded food source, offering approximately 13% protein, 1.8% lipids, and 59.2% starch, along with essential nutrients like manganese, phosphorus, niacin, and B vitamins. India stands as the third-largest global wheat producer, achieving a record 112.74 million metric tons in 2022-23, with a cultivation area of 31.87 million hectares. Maharashtra alone produced 2 million metric tonnes from 860,000 hectares. However, because of things like poor seed quality, waterlogging, salinity, and ineffective fertiliser use, nutrient availability frequently stays below ideal levels even in fertile soils. Additionally, nutrient fixation is made worse by high soil pH and lime content, which restrict crop uptake and reduce productivity.

Biostimulants that are enhanced with fulvic and humic acids are becoming important instruments for improving soil fertility and wheat growth. These compounds enhance microbial activity, water retention, nutrient chelation, and plant resistance to abiotic stressors. Foliar application of biostimulants (Delfine et al. 2005; Muhammad et al. 2019; Yadav et al., 2021) has proven particularly effective, as it delivers nutrients directly to leaves, ensuring rapid absorption and minimizing dependence on soil conditions. By improving plant health and lowering the need for synthetic fertilisers, organic formulations made from fermented materials, such as panchagavya and jeevamrut, also promote sustainable agriculture. (Sobczak, A., et al., 2020). Biostimulants provide a sustainable solution to problems in wheat cultivation, like limited nutrient availability and environmental stresses, by increasing crop performance and nutrient efficiency. (Yaseen, et al., 2011)

Materials And Methods**Experimental Site****Standard methods used for the analysis of physical and chemical properties**

The physical characteristics of the soil, such as the percentages of silt, clay, fine sand, and coarse sand, were determined Using the international pipette method (Piper, 1966) and the textural class was categorised accordingly. A core sampler (Dastane, 1972) was used to assess bulk density, and a pressure plate device (Richards, 1947) was used to quantify soil moisture constants such field capacity (FC) and permanent wilting point (PWP). A double ring infiltrometer (Klute, 1986) was used to quantify the infiltration rate, and the difference between FC and PWP was used to calculate the amount of accessible soil moisture.

For chemical properties, a pH meter (1:2.5 soil-to-water ratio) was used to measure the chemical characteristics of the soil as per with Piper (1966), and a conductivity meter was used to measure electrical conductivity (EC) (Jackson, 1973). Available potassium (K₂O) was calculated using the neutral ammonium acetate method (Hanway and Heidal, 1967), phosphorus (P₂O₅) using 0.5 M NaHCO₃ (pH 8.5) (Olsen et al., 1965), and nitrogen (N) using the alkaline permanganate method (Subbiah and Asija, 1956).

Soil and climatic conditions

The experimental field's land was level and uniform and the soil had 45-cm depth and was well-drained. The selected area is categorised as semi-arid and subtropical in terms of climate. This region is in the scarcity zone, which is defined by semi-arid tropical conditions and an average of 520 mm of rainfall per year that ranges from 317 to 691 mm. Agro-climatically, the region is drought-prone. The average yearly temperature falls between 38°C and 42°C for the maximum and the same range for the minimum. Relative humidity averages in the morning and evening are roughly 57% and 33%, respectively.

Experimental Details

The past three years' cropping history in the experimental field shows a varied crop rotation throughout the seasons. In the 2020–21 cropping year, the summer season was left fallow, while the kharif and rabi seasons cultivated green gramme and cabbage, respectively. In 2021–2022, broccoli was planted in the summer, chickpeas in the rabi, and soybeans in the kharif. In 2022–2023, the field was left fallow in the summer, cotton was planted in the kharif season and wheat was planted in the rabi. A variety of vegetable, cereal, and leguminous crops are featured in this rotation, along with sporadic fallow intervals that may help preserve soil health.

The experiment was conducted using a randomized block design (RBD) with the field prepared as flat beds. The layout included 14 experimental units replicated three times, with each plot having a gross size of $1.80\text{ m} \times 7.5\text{ m}$ and a net size of $1.4\text{ m} \times 7.5\text{ m}$. Treatments were randomly assigned to the plots, and the plan of the experimental layout is illustrated in

Treatment

The experiment consisted of 14 treatments, each replicated three times in a randomized block design. Treatments included a control with 0% recommended dose (RD) of NPK and 100% RD of NPK alone or combined with biostimulants in various forms and application methods. These combinations involved seed dressing with biostimulant powder (1 g L^{-1}) or liquid (2 ml L^{-1}), basal application of biostimulant powder at varying rates (1.25 to 2.5 kg ha^{-1}), and two foliar sprays at the tillering and pre-flowering stages using

Fig : Various growth parameters of wheat observed at the time of harvest.

biostimulant powder (1 to 3 g L^{-1}) or liquid (2 to 6 ml L^{-1}). One treatment combined 75% RD of NPK with basal application of biostimulant powder (1.25 kg ha^{-1}) and two foliar sprays of biostimulant liquid (4 ml L^{-1}). This setup allowed for the evaluation of biostimulant effects on crop performance.

Result And Discussion

Growth Studies

The application of biostimulants considerably improved the wheat growth parameters, such as plant height, tillers per metre, panicle length, and grains per panicle. The combination of two foliar sprays of biostimulant powder at 3 g L^{-1} and 100% RD of NPK produced the highest values (T_{10}), which were closely followed by T_9 (2 g L^{-1} powder) and T_{13} (6 ml L^{-1} liquid). Overall, the administration of biostimulants via seed dressing, soil application, and foliar sprays greatly increased wheat production and growth.

In above figure-

- T₁ Control 0% RD of NPK
- T₂ 100 % RD of NPK.
- T₃ 100 % RD of NPK + SD with BP @ 1 g L^{-1}
- T₄ 100 % RD of NPK + SD with BL @ 1 ml L^{-1}
- T₅ 100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha^{-1}
- T₆ 100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.90 kg ha^{-1}
- T₇ 100 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 2.5 kg ha^{-1}
- T₈ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 1 g L^{-1}
- T₉ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 2 g L^{-1}
- T₁₀ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BP @ 3 g L^{-1}
- T₁₁ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 2 ml L^{-1}
- T₁₂ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 4 ml L^{-1}
- T₁₃ 100 % RD of NPK + Two foliar sprays of BL @ 6 ml L^{-1}
- T₁₄ 75 % RD of NPK + BA of BP @ 1.25 kg ha^{-1} + Two foliar spray of BL @ 4 ml L^{-1}

The average initial and final plant counts per metre were 48.30 and 46.70, respectively. The treatment of 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} at the tillering and pre-

flowering stages (T_{10}) had the largest plant population variation, measuring 49.97 at 15 DAS and 48.26 at harvest. The treatment of 100% RD of NPK + two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 2 g

L^{-1} (T_9) came just after this. The control treatment, which had 0% RD of NPK, had the smallest plant population (T_1).

The highest plant height in T_{10} likely resulted from enhanced nutrient uptake and metabolic activity within the plant. Similar findings have been reported by Yaseen et al. (2011), Surve and Bhosale (2015), Muhammad et al. (2019), Vikas et al. (2019), Yadav et al. (2019), and Jat et al. (2020).

The quantity of tillers, panicle length, and grains per panicle in wheat were all significantly increased by the application of 100% RD of NPK in conjunction with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} (T_{10}). The longest panicle length (7.03 cm), the greatest number of tillers (89.95 and 108.60 at 60 and 90 DAS, respectively), and the greatest quantity of grains per panicle (43.87) were all reported by treatment T_{10} . These outcomes were statistically comparable to those of treatments T_9 , T_{13} , and T_8 , all of which demonstrated significant gains. The control treatment (T_1) had the lowest values for tiller count, panicle length (5.8 cm), and grain number per panicle (around 39.85). Increased meristematic activity, improved nutritional availability, and other factors are responsible for the increases in these growth characteristics.

Fig : Various yield parameters of wheat observed at the time of harvest.

Quality Studies

Various treatments had a substantial impact on the post-harvest wheat's hectolitre weight, protein content, and gluten content. The largest values (24.73% and 8.78%) were found in the treatment 100% RD of NPK with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} (T_{10}), whereas the lowest was found in the control treatment (T_1). The mean wet and dry gluten content was 23.60% and 8.30%, respectively.

Fig : Various quality parameters of wheat observed at the time of harvest.

Conclusion

In comparison to other treatments, the growth, yield, and quality parameters of wheat were considerably enhanced by the application of 100% RD of NPK in conjunction with two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} (T_{10}). The maximum grain yield (49.29 q ha^{-1}) and straw yield (68.22 q ha^{-1}) were achieved by T_{10} , which consistently produced the highest plant height, tiller number, panicle

The 1000-seed weight of wheat was greatly impacted by the use of biostimulants. The treatment with 100% RD of NPK and two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} (T_{10}) had the largest seed weight (41.56 g), closely followed by treatments T_9 (40.85 g) and T_{13} (40.59 g). The control treatment (T_1) had the lowest seed weight (30.05 g), most likely as a result of its short panicle length (Yaseen *et al.* 2011; Surve and Bhosale 2015; Muhammad *et al.* 2019; Vikas *et al.* 2019; Yadav *et al.* 2021; Jat *et al.* 2020).

Yield Studies

The use of biostimulants had significantly influenced the yield of wheat grain and straw. The treatment with 100% RD of NPK and two foliar sprays of Biostimulant Powder @ 3 g L^{-1} (T_{10}) produced the highest grain yield (49.29 q ha^{-1}) and straw yield (68.22 q ha^{-1}), with treatments T_9 and T_{13} coming in close second and third. The control treatment (T_1) had the lowest grain yield (27.49 q ha^{-1}) and straw yield (38.24 q ha^{-1}). Improved nutrient intake, photosynthetic activity, and effective translocation to grains and straw are responsible for the yield gain, which also improves overall physiological performance. (Majathoub *et al.*, 2004; Karenavar *et al.*, 2022)

Similarly, T_{10} produced the highest protein content (12.04%), which was much greater than the control (9.95%), with a mean protein content of 11.50% (Sadaphal *et al.*, 2002; Muhammad *et al.* 2019). Additionally, the hectolitre weight was lowest in the control group (133.00 kg hl^{-1}) and peaked at 136.25 kg hl^{-1} at T_{10} . According to previous research, these increases are probably the result of improved nutritional availability and utilization.

length, grain count per panicle, and thousand-grain weight. Additionally, it improved the qualitative parameters, such as the maximum hectolitre weight (136.25 kg hl^{-1}), protein content (12.04%), dry gluten (8.73%), and wet gluten (24.78%). These findings support T_{10} 's potential to maximise wheat production and quality by demonstrating its superior performance as a result of enhanced nutrient availability and utilisation.

References

1. **Al Majathoub, M. 2004.** Effect of biostimulants on production of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Mediterranean Rainfed Agriculture: Strategies for Sustainability, CIHEAM, Zaragoza*, 147-150.
2. **Dastane, N.G. 1972.** A practical manual for water use research in agriculture. Published by Navbharat Prakashan, Pune-2. pp. 120.
3. **Delfine, S., Tognetti, R., Desiderio, E. and Alvino, A. 2005.** Effect of foliar application of N and humic acids on growth and yield of durum wheat. *Journal of Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, **25**(2): 183-191.
4. **Hanway, J and Heidal, H.S. 1967.** Soil analysis methods as used in Iowa State college. Soil Testing Lab. Iowa. Agricultural University, **57**: 1-31.
5. **Jackson, M.L. 1973.** Soil chemical analysis, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi. 489.
6. **Jat, L., Rana, N.S., Naresh, R. K., Dhyani, B. P. and Jat, M. 2020.** Effect of integrated nutrient management on yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under in Indo Gangetic Plains. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, **9**(6): 1378 1383.
7. **Karenavar, S. S. 2022.** Effect of Humic Acid based Bio-stimulant on growth, yield and quality of kharif rice (*oryza sativa* l.) Under lateritic soils of konkan (Doctoral dissertation, Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli).
8. **Klute, A. (ed.). 1986.** Methods of soil analysis. Part 1 – Physical and mineralogical methods.
9. **Muhammad Bismillah Khan, Muhammad Farooq, Mubshar Hussain, Shahnawaz and Ghulam, 2010.** Foliar application of micronutrients improves the wheat yield and net economic return. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, **12**: 953 956.
10. **Muhammad Tahir, Muhammad Tahir Naveed, Aftab Ahmad Sheikh and Rizwan Maqbool. 2019.** Growth, yield and quality response of three wheat varieties to foliar spray of micro nutrients. *Pakistan Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research Series B: Biological Sciences*, **64B** (1): 49 54.
11. **Piper, C.S. 1966.** Soil and plant analysis. Indian Edn. Hans. Pub. Bombay.
12. **Richards, L.A. 1947.** Pressure membrane apparatus, construction and use. *Journal Agriculturalengineering*, **28**: 45-54.
13. **Shewry, P. R., Halford, N.G., Belton, P.S. and Tatham, A.S. 2002.** "The structure and properties of gluten: An elastic protein from wheat grain". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. **357**(1418): 133 142.
14. **Subbiah, B.V. and Asija, G.L. 1956.** A rapid procedure for the determination of available nitrogen in soils. *Journal of Current Science*, **25**: 259-260.
15. **Vikas Abrol, Singh, A. P., Anil Kumar, Ravinder Charya, Ch Nivasarao, Peeyush Sharma, Brinder Singh, Sanjeev Salgotra, Jai Kapoor and Hemant Dhachich. 2019.** Effect of foliar application of nutrients on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) crop performance, economics, resource use efficiency and soil properties under rainfed conditions. *Advanced Centre for Rainfed Agriculture, SKUAST J, Samba, Jammu and Kashmir*. **81** (1): 133.
16. **Yadav, R. K., Kumar Mahendra, Kumar Saini Pradip, Alok Kumar Singh, Singh A.K., Brijesh Kumar, Pandey, A.K. and Ankit Singh. 2021.** Effect of foliar application of different nutrients on growth and yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under sodic soil. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, **10**(1): 589 594.
17. **Yaseen M., Ahmed, W., Arshad, M. and Ali, Q. 2011.** Response of wheat to foliar feeding of micronutrients. *International Journal for Agro Veterinary and Medical Sciences*, **5**(2):209-220.